

THE AUTHORITY OF STYLE¹

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The scientist questions the validity of narrative statements and concludes that they are never subject to argumentation or proof. He classifies them as belonging to a different mentality: savage, primitive, underdeveloped, backward, alienated, composed of opinions, customs, authority, prejudice, ignorance, ideology. Narratives and fables, myths, legends, fit only for women and children . . . [but] . . . Scientific knowledge cannot know and make known that it is true knowledge without resorting to the other, narrative, kind of knowledge which from its own point of view is no knowledge at all. Without such recourse it would be in the position of presupposing its own validity and would be stooping to what it condemns: begging the question, proceeding on prejudice. But does it not fall into the same trap by using narrative as its authority? (Lyotard [1979] 1984: 27-29).

The narratives offered in social anthropology serve as 'knowledge' of the various expressions of human life and meaning encountered largely by western academics who have journeyed into the 'field' and have ostensibly confronted 'otherness'.

Monographs are written 'after' and as a 'result' of fieldwork – fieldwork being the period of the anthropologist's encounter with the anthropological subject: a time of observation and collection of 'data', and also (often) a time of difficulty and doubt, 'culture shock', loneliness, and confusion. The fieldwork experience is said to distinguish the discipline from other social sciences. Fieldwork is a non-replicable, temporally finite period of close-up scrutiny which has, more and more, become an emblem of 'anthropological sensibility'.

Recently, self-consciousness about the fieldwork experience has intensified the inquiry into methods of presenting ethnographic data. The written product has become an object of study in itself – and this is a positive step because ethnographic writing, while parallel to other modes of writing, is as much a distinctive aspect of anthropology as working in the field. The results of fieldwork are always presented to the readers of anthropology through the text – all our understandings are textual – and thus, self-consciousness about fieldwork must be extended to self-consciousness about textual representations of that work.

This paper is in three sections. The first part is a theoretical foray setting the ground for the second, which is a reading of the work of three contemporary anthropologists. While the second section draws upon the project set out in the first, the project is not fully exploited by these readings of Rabinow, Dwyer, and Fernandez. I develop this later aspect in part three with reference to discussions of the 'text metaphor' in recent essays by Rabinow and Fernandez.

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Becoming so uncomfortable about writing, anthropologists have turned to suggestions from 'outside' the discipline in an attempt to justify what we now do with criticism.² Following Foucault, Said offers a means of examining ethnographic representations without claiming to bypass the inevitable textuality of anthropological knowledge and yet remaining sensitive to political and ethical issues. He writes:

The things to look at are style, figures of speech, setting, narrative devices, historical and social circumstances, not the correctness of presentation nor its fidelity to some great original (Said 1978:21).

Beyond a conventional reading of ethnographic narrative proper, a number of institutional and experiential occurrences may be seen to emerge within the text in the 'style' and 'circumstances' of the document. That is, the ethnographic text is a cultural product surrounded by certain visible technologies – printing, library classification, distribution – and incentives – research programs, ambitions, reader interests – which support the monograph as an academic object. (Even when writing in a tent in the field the ethnographic writer is part of the institution). The text is written in a 'context' and so appears to us as 'book-knowledge' bearing the marks of its surroundings.

It may be that monographs are both true and false records of particular encounters between particular subjects. That the anthropological stories which emerge from these encounters are subjectively bound in stylistic conventions does not distinguish them, on this level, from other stories. A monographic study is a response to certain encounters – with events, actions, meanings, subjects – represented in one (or some) of many possible ways, none of which can be judged against the non-textual 'actual' occurrence. Here fieldwork is a fiction generated by a particular context of writing which presents one representation rather than another. While all writing must make selections, conscious or unconscious, what may be challenged in the absence of an 'actual' is the anthropologist's privileged access to a definitive version of events.

After the above arguments ethnography becomes a genre subject to the criticisms of a variety of readers and ways of reading. Writing is co-constituted with reading, and in a discipline that claims to communicate knowledge of others, to explain the meaning of other practices and beliefs, to write about other manifestations of life, the reader, or receiver, of information must be seen as important from both the writer's and the critic's point of view (Derrida 1985: 31-33). The writer writes for an audience, the critic asks 'how effective is the message given to the audience?' – in both cases analysis must descend upon the ambitions of the work.

The anthropologist's authority to 'tell' about the 'other' depends indirectly, but ultimately, upon the perception, anticipation and sympathy of the reading public (mainly, the 'academic' audience) for whom the author makes an 'autobiographical' definition of 'us' and 'them' (Crick 1982: 15-16). The reader may accept or dismiss the author's claims. Knowing this, the author must present in ways that will be accessible and acceptable; the author must edit and include information according to particular readerly (institutional) expectations. Here the traditional styles and examples of previous writings make this effort somewhat automatic. The coherent monograph is controlled by the selections of the author – "a controlling mode of authority" (Clifford 1982: 142). If the author is conditioned by convention then it is the celebration of authorship – the authority of a particular author rather than a tradition of reading and writing – that can be undermined by the explication of strategies prevalent, and often repeated, in ethnographic texts.

While the building metaphor is in danger of becoming overworked after the various reflexive, theoretical efforts sometimes collected under the label 'deconstruction'³, it is useful to look at ethnographic texts with a fairly literal reading of the insight that 'anthropologists construct knowledge' (Crick 1982: 16). An examination of ethnographic building materials and tool marks, as well as the foundation and excavation work, landscaping and interior design, allows a reading of prefaces, introductions, chapters, conclusions, photographs, bibliographies and indexes, in terms of the constructed text made of 'bits' of information combined according to certain standardised and regulated practices.⁴

Monographs should then be examined for ways in which spaces are specified for the human entities that appear in the text. Classifications which ignore the singularity, and proper nouns which ignore the multiplicity, of subjects (Deleuze and Guattari [1972] 1984: 42), names which label exotica and the exotica of names, definitions of selves and others, manipulated and controlled responses, staged quotations (Clifford 1983: 139) and enforced silences (Foucault [1969] 1977: 138), all co-ordinate an acclaimed signifiable 'truth'. The appearance of subjects in the text is subordinate to certain gestures of location, naming and strategic quotation which confirm the observer's perceptions and prejudices and sustain the dominance of an 'objective' scientific point of view.

To ask how ethnographies "achieve their effect as knowledge of 'others'" (Marcus and Cushman 1982: 25) is to reopen an old debate about the demonstration of 'truth' that goes

back, almost interminably, to ancient Greece. As it was necessary for Plato to turn to narrative to illustrate his insights, so do all articulations have to submit to a structure. The ethnographic narrative turns temporal fieldwork into spatial text, and while an ideal representation would display everything on a single page (Deleuze and Guattari 1983: 17) this is impractical – and probably compromised by the sequential nature of the reader's perception of even a solitary flat space. The temporality of fieldwork and the temporality of reading work on different time scales and so are not directly compatible.⁵ As a recognised rhetorical construction, narrative remains a major means of generating the 'reality' of a subject under discussion. This is amply demonstrated with the neological force of the title *Writing Culture* (Clifford and Marcus 1986 eds); this recent volume is ostensibly about writing *about* culture, but the sense of 'writing culture' as a creative verbal injunction should not be missed. Awareness of these manoeuvres, along with other tropological procedures⁶ invites criticism of the privileged authorial claim implicit in the terms 'description' and 'interpretation' (Clifford 1980: 529).

The author's interpretation and description has been shown as a selective exercise of inclusion and exclusion (Foucault [1969] 1982), which, when exposed, upsets the 'scientific image' of anthropology. Some anthropologists are embarrassed by the realisation that the discipline proceeds largely by elaborate, secretive fabrication. In reaction to this a 'crisis' enters with a privilege into anthropological consciousness resulting in "suicidal rejoicing" for the end of anthropology (Richardson 1975: 527) on the one hand, and a morbid enjoyment of exposing sins – a confessional – on the other.

The 'confession' of 'what really happens in the field' emerged in discussions of methodology in older texts⁷, and has become a central concern in more recent years. There is a subtext to be read in this confessional discourse, as it appears first in prefaces and introductions, and later, in the 'ethnography proper', which reveals an authorial claim for the legitimacy of the ethnographer's project as writer about 'other' people. The confession admits the fabricated nature of the situation but allows the work to continue unchanged.⁸ A detective work that wants to excavate these styles, tropes, mentions of subjects and confessions, is subject to the same dangers as those it points out. Baudrillard finds such projects a simulation of the same old sins (Baudrillard 1983: 15)⁹ and this work may simply reiterate the offences it condemns by selecting three recent (male) writers and reinscribing their importance by subjecting them, rather than others, to the critique. Inevitably I must confess to having chosen to look at only some of the possible ethnographies, length constraints excluding other monographs and many works by women writers which deserve to be included. It would be advisable to remember that this confession may be criticised too. Indeed, criticisms themselves are confessions and provide another text to be read in the same ways, becoming a paradox which spirals into writing against writing. The reflexive ethnographic manifestation of this paradox comes with its own nurtured and fashionable anguished conscience.

There is an ambivalence and necessary responsibility in authority which combines power and duty. The power of the text rests in its ability to fix meanings (to a degree), but this permanence implies a certain extension of obligations and liabilities. Widely distributed texts have greater authority and demand a greater discipline. All writing attracts this increased responsibility, and because ethnography presents its observations in books and articles, anthropology will always be textual and subjected to wide-ranging textual criticisms. The degrees of this ambivalence permeate every statement, and even the least significant can be found out and subjected to criticism.¹⁰ Are we to get indignant because we are 'deceived' by rhetoric while we recognise rhetoric in everything we do? To suffer "the despair of the gambler throwing good money after bad" (Dwyer 1979: 205) because we mourn for the purity of a language not corrupted by the distortions implied by every communication/translation?

This existential (theoretical) conundrum is recognised by Foucault:

By correcting itself, by rectifying its errors, by clarifying its formulations, discourse does not necessarily undo its relations with ideology. The role of ideology does not diminish as rigour increases and error is dissipated (Foucault [1969] 1982: 186).

Given this, it would be easy to turn towards a 'fantastic negativity', and it is conveniently simple to be critical and cynical. Cynicism has its best advantage with writing, though a

paradox of writing critically about writing about 'others' who are known only through writing is not simply cynical. It is difficult for perspective to arrange itself as its own subject without retaining ingrained notions of truth and decision, value and preference, authority and authenticity, and other definitional traps. In examining the presentation of monographs amongst these paradoxes it is not surprising that programatic questions of how to write come up, and then, in pursuit of this 'fantastic negativity', the extension; 'why write?' The tangle born of these fundamental doubts is consistent with a "crisis of representation" (Rabinow 1985: 10) in anthropology, which agonizes over the ethnographer's right to write about others.

Perhaps this crisis need not mean despair. Perhaps the inquiry into rhetoric can enrich writing and reading. Perhaps an increasing consciousness of narrative structures and tropological strategies can generate fresh insights accompanied by a more sophisticated and responsible understanding of the political liberties of the text – for both writers and readers. Here, already fixed texts would be reopened and reread in different ways. While writing retains its semblance of permanence, a succession of readers may challenge this authority by pointing to the temporality of the fixed moment of writing. Here, the 'reader function' creates an oscillation in the text between durability and redundancy. Writing is both forever and specific to each reading. A monograph may be reopened any number of times; "once it is put right out on the table, [it] is a resource not so easily exhausted" (Tedlock 1979: 397).

It is appropriate to applaud Max Weber's comments in his important essay 'Science as a Vocation' where he speaks of a science that admits that its insights will always soon be obsolete (Weber [1922] 1974: 138). Thus the scientific project renounces an ultimate fixation in favour of the ideal of ultimate refinement.¹¹ Similar points might be made through a reading of Camus' *Myth of Sisyphus* (Camus [1942] 1980). While there is no transcendental hope for Sisyphus there is still purpose in his work; he is not daunted by enormity. The eternal question is by no means the privilege of ethnography, indeed all forms of inscription seem to display a degree of reflexive agitation. Whether it be African rituals or Hamlet's 'to be or not to be', it is possible to hear Tolstoy's questioning of 'what to do and how to live'. The anthropological generic equivalent – how to write about others – is just one more simulation. The unresolved and unresolvable quest, of course, pervades this article itself. Not on quite the same level as the struggle of Sisyphus, but this article may be reopened and rewritten again and again, as may each of the monographs it examines. On any one occasion the reader may find any number of anthropological projects within one study.

There are many possible anthropologies; the scope of the discipline is enormous. Ethnography can be read: as an attempt to explain how or why the world appears as it does to different people (Ennew 1976: 61); as an attempt to come to terms with the difference of 'other' cultural and conceptual frames; as an attempt to understand why man can conceive of a perfect society and yet often lives a life of hate and need. Anthropology could be "suggestive qualitative description" (Salamone 1979: 57) or elegant, romantic storytelling. Anthropology can be seen to be rife with distortion and prejudice, but also as an attempt – perhaps the only one – to communicate 'with' rather than 'at' the rest of the world. Richardson's emotional documentation (quoting Martin Luther King – "I am free at last" – and Chief Joseph – "I will fight no more forever") of human meaning is emblematic of the motivation and contradiction of the anthropological project. While the record may be compromised it must still be attempted:

Who will record these things and more?

Who will search for the human secret?

Who will tell the human myth?

Who will, damn it, who will?

(Richardson 1975: 531).

The project I suggest here entails one possible reading among many. It aims to prepare the ground for a future examination of the 'theories' presented in ethnography through criticism of the representation of 'otherness' found in these texts. The argument throughout is that ethnographic fact exists only insofar as it fits into a particular ethnographic (written) project. Ultimately, the next question would be concerned with the status of a theory whose relationship with 'empirical truth' has been undermined. This

introductory paper exploits the tensions of 'writing' to mount a critique founded upon a belief in the importance and value of the communicative endeavour embraced by anthropologists. Here, writing, in a world of texts, becomes a matter of criticism and responsibility, and despite the criticisms (which are far too simple and too short to efface these monographs), the texts I examine must be respected. Also, I must be held responsible for the faults and biases, omissions and selections, of my own critique.

Because we are beginning to write, to write differently, we must reread differently (Derrida [1967] 1982: 87).

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The second section of this paper is a discussion of ethnographies written by Paul Rabinow, Kevin Dwyer, and James W. Fernandez. The aim is to read these authors in the light of the speculations set out above.

Having become frail, existing legitimations are replaced by new ones. The latter emerge from the critique of the dogmatism of traditional interpretations of the world and claim a scientific character. Yet they retain legitimating functions (Habermas [1968] 1978: 99).

In claiming a privilege of the critical consciousness it would be possible to mask an arch-conservatism which reinstates and legitimates the old conventions in a fresh form. Here reflexive and critical approaches to ethnography proceed as a refined voyeurism, patronising 'others', promising to 'give' them voice, and to 'truthfully' represent their lives. Webster has charged that the "arrogance of reflexivity is so monumental it poses as humility" (1983: 193), but even his attack does not, and cannot, call for an end to anthropology. Those who do make calls for such an end still manage to 'be' anthropologists. All 'theoretical' advances seem to shore up to a consumptive intention to represent, for general readership, the 'essence' of the other. Even the calls for 'dialogue' are predicated on western assumptions and couched in academic, logical, literary terms. And dialogue authorized on an intersubjective consensus between subject and author is still a 'consensus' articulated in the author's text, in the author's library, etc. The dialogues with the other (if the 'other' exists?) are directed into our texts via a number of translations — from an 'indigenous' language to English, from spoken to written, from recorder to pen.¹² It can never be too often emphasized that translation is transformation.

In response to the recognition of problems like these, a "growing trend of experimentation in ethnographic writing" (Marcus and Cushman 1982: 25) has resulted in a number of monographs written in 'new' ways. While fruitful, it has been suggested that these attempts are founded on a search for new conventions (an oxymoron?). A basic insecurity at the fall of the old ways leads to a scramble for another secure method. Marcus and Cushman write:

In this emergent situation, ethnographers read widely among new works for models, being interested as much, if not more, in styles of text construction as in their cultural analysis, both of which are difficult to separate in any case (ibid: 26).

Rabinow's *Symbolic Domination* and *Reflections on Fieldwork in Morocco*

In Paul Rabinow's monograph *Symbolic Domination* (1975) the anthropologist examines the history of a Moroccan village and its dominant lineage descended from a seventeenth century saint Sidi-Lachen. A second book, *Reflections on Fieldwork in Morocco* (1977), examines the anthropologist's relationships with the informants of the first book, whose "names have been changed to protect their anonymity" (Rabinow 1977:vi). Although only one 'informant' is mentioned in the 1975 text it is surprising to find only in 1977 that identities have been protected — the validity and extent of this 'fictionalization' is confusing and all Rainbow's proper names are put under a cloud. Is there a town, or indeed a saint, 'called' Sidi-Lachen?

While the second of these monographs attracts more attention to the author because of its 'elegant literary freshness',¹³ both books by 'Paul Rabinow' (why wasn't his own name changed for protection since he implicates himself in sexual and political indiscretions?) should be taken together. Both begin with acknowledgements of disguised

“Moroccan companions” (Rabinow 1975:vi) who “put up with my seemingly irrelevant questions and presence” (Rabinow 1975:vii). Both acknowledge an intellectual debt to Clifford Geertz and others, and both acknowledge a photographic debt to Paul Hyman “for his stunning and perceptive pictures” (Rabinow 1977:vi) and “the insights they provide” (Rabinow 1975:vii). Both are the ‘results’ of an anthropological ‘tour of duty’ in a Moroccan resort.¹⁴ There are, of course, differences, perhaps superficial: *Symbolic Domination* includes a ‘note on transliteration’ which claims that a phonetically accurate system is unnecessary, while *Reflections* does not. Perhaps more important: *Reflections* is to be ‘philosophical’ rather than written in the ‘anthropological’ or ‘historical’ tone claimed by *Symbolic Domination*. The specification of differences between superficial and profound, philosophical and historical etc., is another problem. In order to avoid such tangles a strategic examination of some contrasts of presentation may be helpful.

Symbolic Domination is concerned with the saint Sidi Lachen and his descendants in the village ‘Sidi-Lachen’. The work is ‘ethnographical’, although much material has been ‘pruned’ for inclusion in a later work in association with Geertz (Rabinow 1975:vii) – a prestigious association which has not yet materialized into the promised volume.¹⁵ Maps are included to ‘locate’ the study and other conventions of presentation are followed to provide the image of a coherent and comprehensive ‘whole’. Both Morocco and Sidi-Lachen are constituted as realities for and by the text. The anthropologist (not a tourist) locates a particular circumscribed entity as the subject of his visit, focusing his gaze upon this area, and these people, rather than others. The scene is set with photographs which come before the written text, beginning with the anthropologist himself dressed in shepherd’s clothing (indicating authentic ‘participating’ presence), and followed by photographs of Moroccans, and villagers, some identified, some not. Captions under the photos already describe a tension and “deceptive laughter” (Rabinow 1975:xviii) which at the outset suggests the possibility of getting behind these tensions and deceptions, thus already anticipating and defining the ambition and conclusion of the research project and the book. *Reflections on Fieldwork in Morocco* deals with the anthropologist’s informants; the photographs are scattered throughout the book, identifying subjects, illustrating points, and, in one instance, showing the anthropologist serving tea to “members of the holy lineage” (Rabinow 1977:108) – a representation of anthropological presence more in keeping with the book’s concern with ‘relationships’ with ‘others’. *Reflections* is very much concerned with the gathering of information, the process and procedure of fieldwork, with who gave whom what news. *Symbolic Domination*, on the other hand, is devoid of such acknowledgements, and the historical data which makes up the bulk of the book, small though it is, is unsupported. In this context it is significant that there are no citations of sources. In both, when Moroccans speak it is between quotation marks or italicized. What they say is never referenced to individuals, and most often is only two or three words in the middle of a Rabinow sentence. It is difficult to distinguish a Moroccan voice from the anthropologist’s emphases.

Rabinow’s argument that Moroccans are dominated by the symbol of the saint Sidi Lachen is elaborated in the first historical section of *Symbolic Domination* – ‘Sidi Lachen and his Age’. All the themes found in contemporary Moroccan political struggles are identified in this period. The argument is that “Symbolic submission and the passionate reaction to it have been the main theme in Moroccan history” (Rabinow 1975:6). Subsequent to the life of the saint, events elaborate this main theme (ibid:31), and isolated “tales” serve to confirm the motif; the tale of the Moquaddem Hamid, although “unique” (ibid:41), provides a “very clear symbolization” (ibid:43). Rabinow does not see such unique and isolated moments as contradictions to his supposition of the uniformity of Moroccan politics:

and so the cycle continues. The strength of the image, the clarity of the portrayal, and the clearness of the sentiments are all the more indicative of the difficulty and infrequency of its occurrence (ibid:43).

Following Geertz (1973), Rabinow will not “refuse to approach problems in general terms but [will] seek particularity within the general context” (Rabinow 1975:98). The problem with this is that all particularities can be seen in ways that confirm prior general ideas. The ‘infrequent’ examples such as that of the Moquaddem Hamid, are seen as “basic symbols” which come to demonstrate an “impressive continuity” (ibid:99), despite claims that this is

not an “intellectual terrorism” that would “force events, persons, and acts into the prefabricated moulds which have been proclaimed for them by the observer” (ibid:98). This claim may be evaluated with reference to *Reflections* and its concern with relationships and informants.

One reading of this book, which deserves a longer and less eclectic examination, might see this concern with relationships and informants as the anthropologist’s panacea for the contradictions of his position. He heals his unease about his place as the ‘imperial’ researcher through description of temperamental and emotional interactions with ‘real people’.

The major informant who appears in both books, though his name has been changed, is Ali. There are complications in any discussion of these characters because Rabinow has “collapsed” some informants into others, and some “are left out altogether” (Rabinow 1977:6). There are no clues as to whether ‘Ali’ is an individual or collective identity (perhaps this does not matter; it is up to the reader to accept the ‘reality’ of personalities in the text). In any case, ‘Ali’s’ political motives for helping the anthropologist are spelled out first in 1975 and more clearly in 1977; this must colour the information he provides. It is convenient that Ali “has been, and still is actively involved in all the major conflicts of the last twenty years” (Rabinow 1975:74) and that he is prepared to explain certain things “in great detail and with great relish”, so that “The fights, betrayals, fears, and reprisals which marked the period were listed and embellished in his own inimitable style” (Rabinow 1977:128-9). On some subjects which villagers were reluctant to talk about, Ali would provide information which would then motivate the other village factions to speak:

Once the silence was broken, once a partisan account was given, other individuals and factions felt it incumbent upon themselves to protect their own interests by telling their version (ibid: 129).

The Moroccans’ understanding of the advantage of ‘impression management’ before the anthropologist is evidenced by the strict controls they imposed on Rabinow’s informants. The most powerful lineage provided an “acceptable” informant (ibid:158-9). Rabinow’s claims to accuracy in both monographs are based on his opportunity and ability to contrast the information gained from the ‘acceptable’ informant, with that gained from Ali, who was politically opposed to the main lineage:

One of the main advantages, for the ethnographer at least, of the high level of discord and mutual antagonism which this society has raised to the level of a life-style, is that what admirers of a particular figure will not tell you, opponents often will. Whereas historical exactness is usually not found in either version, the intersection of the portrayals often yields a locus of the value with which the disputes centered (Rabinow 1975:41).

Rabinow is able to sit back, compare the offered information and do simple plus and minus equations to arrive at the likely story behind the exaggerations. What he himself fails to offer in his reflections is a consideration of how his own personal relationships effect how he decides his equations.

It is Rabinow’s central argument that is undermined with the problems of individual and factional manipulation of information. The importance of Sidi Lachen and his descendant’s feelings of decline of *Baraka* (the saint’s charismatic power) are mediated through a triangle of informants who have each selected and intended impressions to foster. Malik represents the lineage, Ali opposes it, and Ben Mohammed represents another point of view. It is this third that complicates Rabinow’s calculations; and serves as an example of how the explanation is constructed via the anthropologist’s relationships.

Ben Mohammed was a young, fundamentalist Muslim intellectual who had “consistently refused to work as an informant” (Rabinow 1977:142). However, Rabinow had long discussions with him concerning the interpretation of Islam and the other villagers’ superficial knowledge and observance of its tenets. This relationship is not portrayed as informant/anthropologist but as one of ‘friendship’ – supported by a quotation on friendship from Aristotle’s *Nicomachean Ethics* (Rabinow 1977:142). This friendship taught Rabinow “more and more”, and in the last months “reached a new emotional and intellectual depth” (ibid:143). Ben Mohammed’s initial “refusal of informant status set up the possibility of another type of communication” (ibid:143). These are brave but unclear

distinctions which Rabinow makes between one type of communication and another and between when an informant is and is not an informant.

Rabinow's discussion with Ben Mohammed turned to the saint. The Moroccan thought that Sidi Lachen's descendants had lost their *Baraka* through ignorance of the teachings of the saint, to their deviation from traditional Islamic ways (while maintaining an exterior semblance of devout practice), and to arrogant reliance on the prestige of their name. In *Symbolic Domination* Rabinow writes that descendants of Sidi Lachen "do not know (nor are they concerned with) the historical details" of the saint's life although "they do have a legend about him" (Rabinow 1975:17). This statement is unsourced and there is no indication of how the information was gained, beyond: "I found . . ." (ibid:17). Not that 'naming' a source would remove doubt from a statement, but it is upon this 'find' that much of Rabinow's argument about the 'symbolic' nature of domination in Morocco rests. The few "very clear symbolization[s]" (ibid:31) of the 'main themes' of 'Moroccan history' (by which is meant events of Moroccan history relevant to the descendants of Sidi Lachen and that village) are effective precisely because they are "unique" (ibid:41) and isolated instances, hence symbolic, rather than part of a 'coherent' history. In this case Rabinow tends towards a notion of 'history' which must be full, factual, comprehensive and linear.

In the 1977 book the question of knowledge about the saint is again discussed but this time it is possible to identify the most likely way that Rabinow came to his conclusions:

Strangely enough the one area of religion about which the villagers proved to be extremely reluctant to talk concerned their own saint, Sidi Lachen Lyussi. I knew that a legend had grown up about him, and nothing seemed safer than to ask his descendants about his exploits and Baraka . . . My inquiries over the months were met with feet shuffling, short replies, and a general sense that this was not something that people were eager to talk about . . . Finally, after a relatively long period in the village, it became clear that . . . even the saint's descendants themselves did not know very much about their progenitor (Rabinow 1977:132).

Rabinow then claims to have inspired the villagers to investigate the matter and compile a history of Sidi Lachen: "some of the students in Fez started to ask around in the bookstores for his works . . . This process of rediscovery of the villagers' heritage was an interesting one to watch" (ibid:133).¹⁶ It is a happy convenience that the villagers decide to compile just the sort of historical record that Rabinow describes in the 1975 book, as if by chance coincidence of interests they happen to do his research for him in exactly the way most amenable to his monographic intentions. One of the searchers of bookshops in Fez could have been Ben Mohammed; he is described as having some knowledge of the saint's work and is a student. It is he who confirms Rabinow's assertion that the villagers are ignorant of the life of the saint rather than reluctant to talk about it (ibid:144). Indeed, it may be that he is the major source of this interpretation and it can be seen that, as a traditionalist muslim, and student, he would have some reason to deride the other 'less devout' villagers' knowledge. It is not certain which way the interpretation should go; Rabinow favours his 'friend's' version. This 'friend' is also the embodiment of "fundamental otherness" for the anthropologist (ibid:162), and from this confrontation and intimate mediation of meanings, 'understanding' is born.

Of his fieldwork relationships, Rabinow comments that they are processes "of intersubjective construction of liminal modes of communication" (ibid:155). The meanings he retrieves are not held by all subjects – "the subjects involved do not share a common set of assumptions, experiences, or traditions" (ibid) – but are negotiated meanings "constructed between us, over time, in order to communicate" (ibid). The problem is, however, that Rabinow has not 'reflected' upon his own (symbolically dominating) role, as writer, in the relationships as much as he might have, as much as he wants us to believe. He says that every cultural fact "can be interpreted in many ways, both by the anthropologist and by his subjects" (ibid:150) but does not underline the privilege of, or the extent to which, his own role, his own relationships, personality, experience, etc., determine which 'mediated' meanings will be presented in his books. And his inscriptions have the authority, from the reader's point of access, of print.

Despite their 'experimental' presentation, Rabinow's books (especially the more radical *Reflections*) seem to reinstate old claims to objectivity. That a new model of textual

construction can do this should alert us to the relative weighting of the adjective 'new' in a textual context. Each book is both different and the same, isolated and part of a whole. On a different level, Rabinow makes claims for the "holistic" coherence of his books, allowing him to justify what is written in earlier chapters with the promise of what is to come. When "the meaning of each chapter depends on what comes after it" (ibid:6), how can anything be taken on its merits at the time? The reader proceeds on trust while the anthropologist is able to presume his credentials as already given. We must question the surety of the concluding chapter which presents the anthropologist's self-congratulatory (and self-confirming) 'recognition' of a "fundamental otherness" (ibid:162) confronted through a journey to Morocco. Rabinow ends with "two subjects facing each other" (ibid:161), but whatever grounds for equality Rabinow would like to emphasize – "Our Otherness was not an ineffable essence, but rather the sum of different historical experiences" (ibid:162) – there remains a separation which any 'intertwining', 'dialogue', or 'sympathetic recognition of differences', does not and cannot bridge because it is Rabinow who writes and the 'other' who is written.

Ethnographic writing is not seen as a highly culture-specific practice but as somehow 'meta-cultural', and where the ethnographer is seen as somewhat independent of a cultural tradition it is possible to construct a form of objectivity on the basis of the internal vacancy of the actor (the writer) who enters into relationships with the 'native informant'. In his foreword to Rabinow's *Reflections*, Bellah makes a suggestion along these lines:

Perhaps the most poignant thing about this book is that by the penultimate chapter it becomes clear that the author (speaking for the cultural, not the personal self) does not have a 'my culture' to complement the indubitably 'your culture' of even the most modernised Moroccan villager. In consolation for that desolating realisation we are offered just a glimpse of the idea that having lost a traditional 'my culture' the modern western intellectual has available the totality of cultures for personal appropriation (Bellah 1977:ix).

While making some interesting points about the feelings of pathos toward their own heritage that may send some anthropologists 'out into the field' in search of meaning, the statement also makes a sophisticated claim for the authenticity and legitimacy of 'European gazing' within other societies.¹⁷ This apologue is another attempt to vindicate the (Malinowskian) ethnographic project. Whether Rabinow saw these implications in Bellah's evaluation of his experiment is not revealed.

In a more recent essay Rabinow has written on the "crisis of representation" (Rabinow 1985:10) in anthropology, dismissing the insight that anthropologists employ literary conventions (ibid:5) as not "inherently crisis provoking" (idem). Following Foucault, he says: "the myriad forms of embeddedness of language in fields of power and truth will not go away through mere craft" (ibid:2). Despite his recognition of these 'fields' of research,¹⁸ he shies away from them in this essay, suggesting the exhaustion, or failure, of the 'literary criticism' line of inquiry and favouring a more 'power' oriented approach. If this dichotomy were recognised, then Rabinow may be seen as making a valid development and departure from his earlier experiments, but must we accept this portrait of the situation?

Rabinow has identified two trends in the examination of the "conventions of how anthropologists convey their material and establish their authority" (Rabinow 1985:1). The first trend corresponds with the sort of ethnographic writing he attempted in *Symbolic Domination* and *Reflections on Fieldwork in Morocco*. Though he does not directly refer to his own work – he makes instead a footnote reference to June Nash (1979) – he is not embarrassed to call these:

unpretentious and highly successful attempts at integrating other voices, photographs and a certain ethnographic humility into a basically standard ethnographic presentation (Rabinow 1985:1).

The second 'trend' does not get this (unpretentious and humble) praise, subjected rather to the inclusion of a bracketed derogatory or sarcastic clause "(or so they proclaim)". Rabinow describes the:

more ambitious programmatic calls, heavily influenced by deconstructive practices, which seek (or so they proclaim) truly radical recasting of ethnographic writing (ibid).

From clues in Rabinow's tone it seems that he heavily favours the first of these two options.

In the face of the crisis of representation, and the critical reflexive habit it has endangered, Rabinow hopes that the period of 'deconstruction' will pass quickly (ibid:12) on the grounds that the insight that anthropologists use literary devices is "interesting" but no longer provocative of any great challenge. The 'deconstructive turn' is derided as if it were only an academic version of divination and witchcraft accusation, laying bare the entrails of the text, a superstitious futility which does not influence how anthropology must be practised. A literary rather than a political activity, Derrida and Foucault are appropriated by English departments (at Yale, etc.). On the other hand, some do recognize that 'witchcraft' beliefs have a political meaning and consequence, just as accusations of fraud influence conceptions of anthropological prestige and authority.

Were the 'crisis' engendered by a recognition of the responsibilities and prejudices bound up with writing, Rabinow's distancing of himself from the problem would sound like a wish to avoid the recognition of guilt and to be able to write naively again. Is it legitimate to shrug off the realisation that every word written in 'science' may be fabrication of one type or other? Is it possible to say there are no interesting differences between science and fiction (Rabinow 1985:5, following Rorty 1983) without sacrificing an inquiry into the political implications of such constructions? The very 'fabric' of writing style slips out of focus here. Rabinow seems to retain the idea of a separation between writing and politics at some ill-defined level, along with other distinctions which might be questioned, like that between theory and practice when he writes 'programmatically':

If in the last five years we have seen important work showing us specific ways beyond the transparency of language, I think it is now time to take those advances and move back into the world (Rabinow 1985:12).

The exact dividing line between 'important work' and the 'world' which we must go 'back into' is not made clear, and there is no agreement as to the ways 'beyond transparency' if that is even possible (or necessary). Leaving these matters unclear may be acceptable if not for the implicit specification of a 'world' in which anthropology may or may not function. It must be agreed that anthropologists could fruitfully examine their own 'careers', publication, citation, the politics of tenure, etc., but it would be an error to think that the literary or 'textual metaphor' would not be informative in this area.

When Rabinow says:

Making textual production the guiding metaphor of the anthropological encounter risks serious distortion. The overwhelming majority of fieldwork encounters are not about the mutual production of texts (ibid: 6),

he glorifies an ideal image by taking a monomorphic and literal reading of text production and refusing to see hierarchical and asymmetrical manifestations of meanings as text. There is no egalitarian text because there is a hierarchy of readers and so there can be no serious suggestion that texts are beyond political discussion. Rabinow finds little value in repeating the fact that "we can never avoid the author function" (ibid:3) but also refuses the controversy of the reader. This is unusual because it would seem to have been in Rabinow's (theoretical/practical?) interests, and within his competence, to push his 'reflections' further. Instead he claims to identify the failure of contemporary social science to achieve a "paradigm take-off" (Rabinow and Sullivan 1979:4) and notes, on the basis of his own observations, that paradigms of experience and explanation refuse to yield to ones of discourse, dialogue and polyphony, because:

the older canon is being rigorously defended in most anthropology departments. Defended, more often than not, through reproduction of older paradigms strongly reinforced by a wide variety of sanctions (Rabinow 1985:7).

These words come dangerously close to echoing an apology for conservatism and an avoidance of difficulty: because the problem will not go away it does not bear examination. With Rabinow, anthropological 'science' is legitimated again. At the same time as pointing out that "advocates of experimental writing themselves produce texts which are resolutely academic and traditional in form" (ibid: 12) he himself claims, and is acclaimed, as the writer of an experimental ethnography – which is, or inevitably becomes, academic and traditional.

Rabinow backs into a kind of impasse here as he makes a genre out of his own kind of criticism. Whether what he has to say is new or not, he is not denied, and does not refuse,

the opportunity to publish his contemplations on ethnography. The essay contributed to the volume *Writing Culture* is evidence of this, and interesting it may be, although his characterization of Rorty's efforts as mere "edifying conversation . . . [which] . . . tells us very little . . . perhaps because there is very little to tell" (Rabinow 1986:236) seems somewhat impolite. Not the sort of utterance that will generate sympathy for a "speciality . . . currently in the process of self-definition" (ibid:242). However, Rabinow is no longer clearly concerned with 'textuality', although he is still bound up with texts and textual criticism. There seems to be a tone of condemnation in his writing which could be the echo of a struggle for prominence and prestige in a specific genre of textuality, and which serves two immediate purposes; first, to differentiate Rabinow's own efforts from those of the 'deconstructive-semiotic' persuasion (he admits that this is a vague term (idem)); and secondly, to dismiss those 'deconstructive' practices as a "tactic in the field of cultural politics" (idem) which, he says, should be understood in sociological terms. Rabinow does not, in fact, manage to 'understand' these practices away, although the article provides a useful survey (Rorty, Clifford, Jameson, Foucault, Lyotard, Bourdieu, Strathern, etc.); it is little more than a good review. Rabinow outlines his differences from, at the same time as producing an article which helps create, a 'community' or "federation" (ibid:261) of interpretation. He writes: "In closing, I simply mark the space" (idem) and leaves the impression that he is about to move on and beyond. To politics? To where? We must become alert to the tension invoked here and beware of the superiority proclaimed by the advocates of the 'new' which misses out on the benefits and creativity still extant and possible in that which is derided as the 'old', and vice versa. Is there such a strict separation between these old and new, or between text and politics? We need to look closely at our concepts of continuity and progress and see what advantages accrue to those who wield the terms.

Dwyer's *Moroccan Dialogues*

Rabinow acclaims Kevin Dwyer's *Moroccan Dialogues* as "the most radical post-structuralist text we have to date" (Rabinow 1985:3), and as a major confrontation with the problem of how to write anthropology. *Moroccan Dialogues: Anthropology in Question* (1982) could be seen, however, as a failure revoking its own experimentalism within its own covers. (Such paradox and contradiction should be applauded if it is more than staged, tortured intellectual *angst*). In any case, whether the book is 'post-structural', successful, a failure, and/or both, the 'radical experimentalism' of the monograph creates an anthropological hero for bookstores and library shelves. The front cover carries a photograph of a Moroccan male, presumably Faqir Mohammed, subject of eleven recorded and transcribed interviews – 'dialogues' – contained in the book. This Faqir is the "Other" with whom Dwyer 'interacts'. Dwyer wanted "to be sensitive to the Other's voice at the earliest stage possible, to not stifle it within the constraints of a rigid research project, and to respect its integrity" (Dwyer 1982:xvi). To this end the interviews are transcribed with only minor editing – the removal of politically sensitive discussion – and this 'transcription' manufactures a sense of comprehensive and conclusive exposure to a 'total', 'real', 'subject'. But there are no conclusions possible, however desperately we wish to draw them.

Dwyer's is an interesting and important project which claims to "expose the deficiencies of the usual anthropological interpretations" (ibid:xvii) where:

Anthropological analysis is a constructive activity because the anthropologist brings to the activity particular interests and concerns and constructs interpretations of social phenomena in the light of these interests (ibid: 261).

Recognizing that even the questions of an interview may be "defined by the needs of western institutions" (ibid:xvii) and western interests, Dwyer attempts to proceed without pre-determined questions, taking his cue "from the answers he receives" (idem) and the events he witnesses. A rigid research project with pre-determined interview questions would be "too coercive" (ibid:41). But while Dwyer travels to Morocco planning to "simply spend more time with people I had come to care about and to enjoy myself with" (Dwyer 1979: 217), he enters carrying a tape-recorder and camera, and has intentions which are not those of a 'simple' holiday-maker. Even forgetting these 'technological' coercions¹⁹, his responses will still be defined by western interests and in this aspect the

book is "meant to be vulnerable to criticism" (ibid:xxiii). It is a very elegant twist for Dwyer to remark that "this book's failures should, perhaps, be counted in its favour" (Dwyer 1982:41). This, he claims, is not said to "hedge bets" (idem), but to point out that even the interview transcription does not exclude certain interests. This pretentious disclaimer should not be allowed to exclude criticism of the faults of the book's (that is, Dwyer's) presentation. But should such criticism be appropriated and "counted in its favour" (idem)? This suggestion challenges the specificity of the notion of criticism by others, and monopolizes the evaluation of its own authorship (the right to write). Anthropologists, of course, and some students may have little else to do when they are not in the 'field' but criticize (if there is a separation between reading and seeing). Isn't the text written in a critical context and for a critical audience? – and critical reception does not suggest that the *Moroccan Dialogues* should not have been written, but rather questions how the text was 'written', by whom, why, where and when, and for whom?

The deficiencies of the usual anthropological interpretations are, according to Dwyer, to be counteracted by emphasizing the 'dialogic' nature of work in the field. Anthropologists engage in dialogues with 'others'. Thus the transcribed dialogue is seen as the purest representation of anthropological contact. When Dwyer proposed to the Faqir that the taped conversations made on a visit three and a half years earlier be published, the Faqir's assent is transcribed in dialogic form (ibid:xix-xxi). In this manner the assent is authenticated, even though tone and context are not discernible in the written words. The assumption is that the cassette recorder cannot misrepresent the 'actual' spoken, a technology of authority, its support behind each of the eleven dialogues in the book testifies to the validity of the word. Like the photograph, the tape is 'incontrovertible'. While the tone of the dialogues themselves cannot be retrieved from the transcribed word, some context is provided. The recordings were made in a two month period in the summer of 1975.

In 1969 Dwyer first arrived in Morocco to do doctoral research. This trip lasted two years, the first two months in the capital, Rabat, studying Arabic, and then six months in a large town Taroudannt. Eighteen months were spent in the village of Ouled Filali with weekly visits to Taroudannt to see his wife. It was towards the end of this trip – 1971 – that Dwyer first met the Faqir. Two years passed before Dwyer returned to Morocco and stayed with the Faqir's family for one month. This one month field trip was to conclude doctoral research. Dwyer's relationship with the Faqir "had no explicit place in my dissertation" (ibid:21), but is spoken of as a long and consolidated one: "we had discussed such issues over the years" (ibid:202) – here 'over the years' refers to, at most, five months separated by two breaks of two years, and only in the two months of 1975 were there regular dialogues.²⁰ These occasions were fitted into the Faqir's schedule of farming morning and afternoon, when the Faqir "had a little time" to "make noise" with the anthropologist (Faqir, in Dwyer 1982:15), often after a nap, just before lunch, excluding market days which were three days a week. Dwyer wants to be sensitive to the 'Other's' voice (he often capitalizes 'other' as a generalized proper name) but the recorded relationship is not a long one (four morning sessions for four weeks – probably, at most only between sixteen and twenty-five hours, we are not told – and all this while he is completing his PhD), it is not clear that the anthropologist is sensitive to the Faqir's time restrictions and he does not, despite attempts, pursue the Faqir's interests but his own.

It is not sensitivity to the Faqir's 'voice' that produces the map on pages 4 and 5. How can a map be a product of dialogue? Large sections of the monograph are not about the Faqir, nor presented as the result of dialogue but as 'participations' and 'observations' (e.g. Dwyer 1982:68-71, 195-201). The presentation of the chronology of the Faqir's life is perhaps more 'dialogic' but is also evidence of the imbalance of this dialogue as it is reproduced in the text; these are not the Faqir's words and, in what is a clearer indication of who 'speaks' in this dialogue, the Faqir does not present a chronology of the anthropologist. The Faqir does not have the privilege of conclusion or of summary; he cannot respond to Dwyer's introductory comments; the Faqir does not write the preface, the contents, the index, and he does not include a theoretical essay on anthropology. He is not even properly named throughout the monograph, Dwyer prefers the general term 'Faqir' to the more specific and personal 'Mbarek'. When Dwyer writes "the Faqir and I" (Dwyer 1979:218) he could mean any Faqir, the generality provides a sense of this relationship

being 'typical' of encounters with 'wise' Moroccan men. At the same time, a constructed and personalised 'Faqir' is presented only as a limit:

Consequently, although I had certainly initiated the whole process of formulating and articulating the meaning of our mutual experience, just as I had initiated our relationship by coming to Morocco in the first place, my control over that meaning was checked by his words and answers just as his hospitality in receiving me into his house had helped to structure my experience in Morocco (Dwyer 1982:215).

While a certain 'character' is developed in the narrative, the Faqir is shut out of the dialogue as an initiator, he only helps with accommodation and his 'words and answers' are only a limit to the anthropologist's control. Despite this, Dwyer claims, with little evidence, that: "the Fakir's deeper aims, which I am in no position to summarize, were somehow satisfied too" (ibid:xvi). These unidentified and unsummarized deeper aims seem as absent from the dialogue as the Faqir is absent. The Faqir is recorded as saying:

As for me, I know that I am not concerned with a single one of your questions. I know that these questions serve your purposes, not mine . . . If I had the time, I would always talk, I've told you that. Even about turtles. This is your goal not mine . . . All of this is good, all of it, because it serves your purposes. But for me, not a single thing serves mine (Faqir, in Dwyer 1982:226).

It is to Dwyer's credit that he includes this passage which contradicts what he has said²¹, yet, into this moment Dwyer interjects with a footnote (another privileged tool of the anthropologist – the Faqir contributes no footnotes) which claims the Faqir's denial as evidence of the opposite: "The Faqir had said almost the exact same thing, that his work was important for others and not for him, when he described his term as village *moqaddem*" (Dwyer 1982:226n). Absent from this second take – second temporal playing of the dialogue – the addendum to the recording, the Faqir cannot respond to the insinuation.

Dwyer's attitude to the voice of the 'Other' excludes the Faqir from the dialogue in many ways. One extreme case is the persistence of interviewing itself. The Faqir falls asleep at the end of one recording session, a fact Dwyer repeats three times (ibid:16, 237, 288). This is symptomatic of the anthropologist's position in regard to the 'other' conceived as a resource waiting to be tapped. In wanting to represent the other's voice with as little intervention as possible Dwyer tries to avoid premeditated questions which would be "too coercive, because it would force the Faqir's thoughts into categories he had no say in forming" (ibid:41). This aim is naive in two ways. Firstly, to think that an absence or looseness of questions will avoid coercion while the anthropologist, tape recorder switched on, paper and pencil at hand, sits expectantly before the Faqir, is to neglect the effect of 'mere' anthropological presence. Secondly, to think that the Faqir's thoughts will be 'forced' into categories "he had no say in forming" denies all autonomy and intelligence to the Faqir, as if the Faqir were incapable of a Moroccan response to a predetermined question. Both assumptions are 'orientalism' (see Said 1978). Beyond this there is also the problem of an 'Other' for Dwyer as a counterpoint for ethnographic reflection and some notion of fidelity to an 'Other' as a person encountered. These two 'Others' merge and separate throughout the book.

The monograph remains, after all Dwyer's intentions, a conventionally packaged product. Like all such products the brand specifications determine the content. The typographic layout reflects Dwyer's position in the dialogue, his questions and interjections are italicized and those he thinks more important are in bold black type. Of course, Dwyer did not say these things in bold black type – does it matter that they are post-recording emphases? All the Faqir's responses are in uniform plain type, never bold, never italicized, often interrupted. There are no quotation marks around his words but they are not needed, shades of grey function just as well to enclose native words. As these sections of the monograph are meant as the 'substance' of the 'Other's' voice, it is their presentation more than anything else that indicates who is the author of the book, and the dialogues.²² Wanting to avoid a shielding of the self which will "disarm the Other" (Dwyer 1982:xxii), Dwyer's choice of typescript does just what he wanted to avoid. Dwyer has the privilege and right to put his 'self' in a vulnerable position – a sort of fashionable martyrdom which provides a covering excuse to write while recognising the immorality of

writing. Given the constraints of the situation – of publishing, writing, presentation, the whole monolithic expectation of coherence and order, etc., it is not surprising that Dwyer ‘fails’.

However, ‘failure’, for Dwyer, is not seen as a failing, and so he avoids serious criticism. He applauds himself, or his book, for challenging an anthropology which is “taking itself too seriously” (ibid:287), and he congratulates his “earnest” but “superfluous . . . theoretical argument”, but then claims that his “serious tone was inevitable” (idem). Telling us once again that the Faqir falls asleep “after a summer filled with serious talk” (ibid:288), Dwyer seems stuck rather than confused. He goes back to Morocco having condemned anthropology.

To seek a text that might challenge traditional views regarding the objectivity of the event, the neutrality of the anthropological inquiry, the invulnerability of the anthropologist, would necessarily be to challenge anthropology itself and its role as the preeminent intellectual arena for articulating the encounter between people of different cultural backgrounds (ibid:216).

The author still articulates an ‘anthropology’. His challenge is conventional and readily absorbed (i.e. by Rabinow). This must raise some anarchic questions. Why does Dwyer write at all? Why doesn’t he/why can’t he separate himself from the text? He wants to break out of the confinements of anthropological practices and expectations but he cannot break with anthropology and he cannot break out of the necessity of breaking up the text in a conventional way. Why write?

Along with the separations between question and answer, there are also those between dialogue and prelude, introduction and text, between chapters, and between the two major sections of the book – ethnography and reflexive philosophy, this last separated by a group of photographs. All of these manifestations are skipped over with the question: “Where, then, did the Faqir end and Kevin begin?” (ibid:215). Amidst all conventional separations, the one Dwyer fabricates between a ‘self’ and an ‘Other’ dissolves, along with the rest, into the creativity of the author. They are orchestrated divisions, the anthropologist is the identity that emerges to preside over both typefaces, both introduction and text, ethnography and theory. Each of the eleven dialogues has its own introduction and conclusion provided by Dwyer, as well as there being a general introduction and a ‘theoretical’ conclusion. There is nothing beyond Dwyer’s orchestration. There is no Faqir, no self ‘and’ other, except in a text classified ‘anthropology’, ‘ethnology’, ‘ethnology-Morocco’, ‘Morocco – social life and customs’, catalogued under Dwyer K., and printed in “Basherville text and display type” by “Universal Lithographers Inc.” (ibid:298). Should there be any concern that the Faqir is now codified in specific ways and serves, in his manifestation as Dwyer’s book, as a successful academic cultural artifact?

Fernandez’s *Bwiti: An Ethnography of the Religious Imagination in Africa*

A first, and most striking, authorial impression is the weight of James W. Fernandez’s recent monograph. *Bwiti* is an intimidating 730 pages; sheer size suggests a work of dedication. The index runs to 55 computer collated pages and this itself is a technology of authority. Other conventions, such as figures, photos, linguistic note and six contents pages, anticipate a wealth of detail about a people who live in an “obscure backwater of the globe” (Fernandez 1982:xix). To the ‘Fang’, of course, it is no backwater but home; the anthropologist constructs the environment from his own point of view. Another instance of this construction is displayed on the front cover – the photograph of a mysterious looking *Bwiti* religious cult leader. The presence of this imposing figure is an effect of the camera angle Fernandez has chosen. The presence of the author can be read in the framing of this image, it is a simple thing to imagine that the photograph must have been posed with the anthropologist at ground level lying on his stomach – perhaps thinking as he set up the shot that this would provide a good cover for his intended book. The savannah plains, lonely tree and tumultuous sky, behind the figure suggest an alien continent, the robes of the *Bwiti* leader, the thrown out chest, the expression on his face, all these signs enclosed in this photograph suggest, following the subtitle of the ethnography: *The Religious Imagination in Africa*.²³

It is these first impressions that lay the foundation for the reader’s acceptance of the anthropologist’s authority to present ‘knowledge’ about Africa. The mysteries that are

promised on this first page presume an authorized interpreter who, having 'been there' and 'understood', can guide us through the museum display of his text. While many of the conventional anthropological themes are followed, Fernandez also takes other 'theoretical' concerns into greater account, indeed giving them central place in his inquiry. For example, he examines the conceptions of social and categorical 'space' held by a number of individuals both among the Fang generally and among the *Bwiti* cult (ibid:chps 3, 4, 14, 15) and he gives extensive space to considerations about women throughout. This second interest may be the influence of his wife who, although unnamed, is identified, along with the ethnographer himself, as an interacting member of the group studied.²⁴ The brief biographies of *Bwiti* characters include comments upon the position of anthropologist: "He asks too many questions and is always doing paperwork. 'What does he want really?'" (ibid:20), and his "number one wife" who: "cooks with the other women, goes to the plantation and fishes and bathes down at the river. She is better loved than her nosy husband" (ibid:20). It may be that the husband and wife roles in the field are stereotyped, but at least they are not written up as invisible observers, but as actors. Fernandez makes an interesting entry into the area, describing the political intrigues and implications of his choice of residence from his own viewpoint, and as far as he can, from what Fang tell him (ibid:6). Arrival anecdotes, however they are reworked, still remain a staple introduction to ethnographic authenticity.

Fernandez's interest in metaphor, upon which he published a long essay in 1974, is followed up in this monograph, leading to an extensive, even exhausting, documentation of *Bwiti* metaphors. Some examples from the many are: the *Bwiti* chapel as metaphor for the hunters' lodge (Fernandez 1982:499), or as womb (ibid:426), eating as adultery (ibid:173), fruit as breast (ibid:558), lightning and thunder as sex (ibid:334), thinking as hunting and forest craft (ibid:502) and Fang themselves as the forest (ibid:100-1). In *Bwiti* Fernandez sees a metaphoric creativity where traditional images and colonial/missionary influences are "tied together" by the "masters of *Bwiti*" to construct an "overarching integrity" and a secure "whole" (ibid:462-3). *Bwiti* is represented as a sort of social philosophy which responds to and deals with the changes and challenges of the contemporary situation to make sense of the world in which Fang live:

by embarking by metaphoric enactments along a path of performances that sequentially and aptly transform the participants' focus of attention and their sense of quality in self, in others, and in situations. This moves them finally to an overarching sense of solidarity in the sacred society of *Bwiti* in which they act and of integrity in the cosmos in which they dwell (ibid:563).

This is, of course, Fernandez's impression. Perhaps his wish or need to see coherence in his object of study. He is prepared to acknowledge that his account is only one interpretation guided by his own interest in metaphor and his interest in trying to discover the Fang response to the colonial/missionary presence. It is convenient that these two interests converge on the *Bwiti* cult; again this may be a subjective coincidence:

The point is that the student of *Bwiti* always learns rather different things about this religion not only according to the informant with which he works but depending upon where he begins his analysis . . . For that aspect of the religion with which he begins will tend to frame his progressive understanding as he or she seeks, like the *Bwiti* sermonizer himself, some integrity in his materials (ibid:563).

Not the only limitations, but it is well to recognise them. Fernandez can only partially confront the *Bwiti* universe of meaning where, to his mind, symbols:

give it a resonance and complexity, a plenipotentiary quality, which the discussion and the sequence of metaphors, or any mode of knitting together the whole, does not fully capture (ibid:564).

The plenipotentiary nature of Fernandez's position as observer is undermined in the self-criticism of the latter part of the passage, a criticism which might be made of all anthropological explanations, perhaps of all writing. It is these kinds of comments, which appear in his monograph but seem to be worked out in fuller form in the shorter papers, which make this author relevant here. There is a certain continuity in his work, but also interesting disjunctions. The essays seem to develop some points to the neglect of others – as if it should be demanded that there be consistency.

The linearity of writing cannot capture the life-world in full, as Fernandez has recently noted in an essay on his "misgivings" about the text as metaphor for ethnography:

a great deal of the rich complexity of communication is lost in 'writing it down' . . . Even the most complex orthographic system, abundant with diacritical marks, cannot capture all the nuances of human communication *in vivo* (Fernandez 1985:16).

The problem is that the categories anthropologists use – totemism, witchcraft, kinship, metaphor – may be "not only self-referential but self-serving and self-replicating" so that "by employing them we contribute more to our solidarities than to theirs" (ibid:21). All of the conventions of ethnographic presentation participate in this textual confirmation, including those used by Fernandez even when he attaches 'reflexive' disclaimers that point out limitations. There must be acknowledgement that there is still something contrived in continuing to use the case study to extrapolate generalizations about culture, to extend from "experiences with a small group of individuals to an understanding of broader aspects of the society" (Fernandez 1982:7). This may be an inevitable problem bound up with the very notion of ethnography which presumes to explain or translate from one context to another.

There are no criteria of authentication that cannot be undermined. Something will always be lost in translation and yet anthropologists continue to find ways to justify, to authorize, the value of their transactions. That Fernandez can point out that anthropologists have "been beguiled since time immemorial" by a notion of truth in a "world we have constructed and reconstructed by our methods" (ibid:xix-xx) sits strangely between his earlier claim that: "anthropologists . . . by reason of the character of fieldwork, have a very rich sense of reality" (Fernandez 1974:132) and his more recent affirmation that anthropology studies life "among people" rather than in the illusory space of the academy (Fernandez 1985:15). But then perhaps writing is forever in contradiction. To separate academy and reality, writing and reading, text and world, sign and meaning, supports a hierarchical distance between 'academic' and 'other' which is misleading and privileges the position of the author. When Fernandez complains that Ricoeur's 'model of the text' (Ricoeur 1981) is in danger of leading anthropology back into the academy (Fernandez 1985:25) he forgets that he takes his textuality into the field with him, i.e., he takes photographs, speaks, interacts, etc., with the intent to publish. There are also, after all, people in the academy; it is not a separate part of the world, whoever may like to think it is so. And ultimately it is an important place for anthropologists to study because it has libraries full of anthropological monographs – including one by James W. Fernandez.

Fernandez wonders whether any further working of the "terrain" of the text metaphor "would not be superfluous" (ibid:26n), yet finds it worthwhile to publish on the subject in the form of a polemic against Ricoeur. It may be that he takes Ricoeur's 'model of the text' too literally, despite his earlier work on metaphor (1974). What he understands by the 'reading' of behaviour and meaning is too easily transferred into an unproblematic written reality. Fernandez claims to be able to identify and separate a 'native voice' within the ethnographic production from his own articulations. He stresses the importance of 'dialogue', saying:

the voices of that interlocution must be present in some form in the final form of our work to be sure that we do not wilfully substitute our own voice for those local voices (Fernandez 1985:20).

Fernandez retains the ideal of an anthropology that, "if it was practised right [would] return . . . from the field with much recorded text, recorded as faithfully and as accurately as method and rapport would allow" (ibid:15). These recorded texts are the "local voices" to be allowed expression through the anthropologist's conscious effort at "turn taking" (ibid:23). They are not to be distorted by the analyses applied by practitioners of the 'textual approach' who monopolise control by insisting on 'reading' and 'interpretation', which simply sets up a new (but false) objectivity. Fernandez seems to have mixed up his metaphors here; the "attitudes of distance, removal and irony" he finds in the 'model of the text', are said to be an "ethnocentric celebration of tradition" (ibid:15), but at the same time he bases his project on a separation between traditions, and between 'us' and 'them'. While it can be agreed that it is "high time that we tried to come to terms fair-mindedly with 'otherness', with the achievements of other traditions" (idem), there is

no reason to think that Fernandez has moved away from the 'reading of meaningful action' necessarily associated with his position. If Fernandez feels uncomfortable with his place in the 'academy' why does he write? Why write for the academy? Again, why write at all? We all write our worlds. In trying to distance himself from the institutional underpinnings of anthropological work he alienates himself from the cultural frame out of which this work originates, and away from this tradition he makes a claim for status as part of a "transcultural elite" (Geertz's phrase 1968:149). It is still possible to 'read' this as ethnocentrism. If we must, as Fernandez puts it, "be aware of the various pressures that prevail upon us to change our perspective and our pronouncements as we move from speaking with those present to speaking about those who are absent" (Fernandez 1985:20), then it is necessary to continue to explore the implications of representing what is seen in the field in texts. Could Fernandez think that 'reality' is constructed any differently than texts? If "'Being there' is mainly what anthropology is about" (ibid:19), this can only be known by the 'anthropological community' through writing. Anthropology is 'writing about being there' and is a disclosure of a particular world. 'Being there on the shelf' is mainly what anthropology is about – otherwise Fernandez would not write such big books. The burden of this paper has been to underline this insight. Ethnographies are the published and bound construction of authorial presence.

* * * *

Rabinow and Fernandez, in proclaiming the exhaustion of the reflexive text metaphor, fall towards the expected conservative moves of apologists for a 'science' wavering on the verge of taking recent developments (for instance, the work of Deleuze and Guattari, Baudrillard, Derrida, and so on), seriously, but still mesmerised by the hope of a conclusion and the possibility of definitive statement. They would already abandon a project only just begun and by no means complete – nor perhaps with a hope, or reason, for completion. This last is the catch-all, the enabling crisis of science identified by Weber. Rather than halt the critique of ethnographic rhetoric in support of a "positivist ethnographic ideology" (Webster 1983:197), the project should be extended.

Marcus and Cushman provide good reasons for keeping this project in focus for both writers and readers: "For the ethnographic writer, an awareness of rhetorical issues, however rhetorically stimulated by critics, could enrich the personal thought process that goes into producing a text" (Marcus and Cushman 1982:57). And: "For the reader of ethnographies, a critical sensitivity to issues of rhetoric can only enhance the subtlety with which anthropological knowledge in ethnographic form is routinely assessed" (ibid:57-8). We are confined to reading about where we have been. (And this is yet another argument for writing adventurously and not revoking the promises made in experiment. If discourse discloses – through language, old metaphors, history – it also creates – new metaphors).

Rhetorical tropes and metaphors need not lose their generative capacity just because they become familiar. They should, instead, be kept at 'boiling point', as we keep on 'cooking the books'. There is no need to be frightened of contradictions in writing. Rabinow and Fernandez seem to have become embarrassed by their embeddedness in rhetoric. Perhaps they suffer from some discomfiting nightmare that when every single word they write can be exposed to criticism they will be obliged to abandon their typewriters and wander off into their African hills – some sort of 'fidelity' to a called bluff. Alternatively, they may turn into caricature anthropologists sitting in their professorial armchairs lamenting the good old days of science and method. For these authors, the text metaphor is now obvious and claimed to be obsolete, but upon examination of both their 'experimental' works and their more recent (advanced) essays, text production can be seen as the continuous guiding principle of anthropological work, and so it remains at all times. The ethnographer is a writer in the field and can never forget this. The ethnographer's problems with writing can be seen at the boundary between a new creativity and a hesitant conservatism, both courageous and regressive, adventurous and resigned. These difficulties are the condition of all writing – bound in an old language trying to say something new – looking both ahead and behind. This sense of a history of writing may be what keeps modern writers on the brink.

Rabinow and Fernandez want to turn to studies of "power and privilege" so as to

“move back into the world” (Rabinow 1985:12), but these ‘moves’ cannot extricate them from the worldly politics of textual production and dissemination. If writing is not a global political activity then what is? The inquiry into narrative politics, and the exploration of narrative alternatives it generates, provides a context in which to begin to rescind the definitional prejudices and privileges of ethnographic production. Texts are political entities because they are the produce of politicised writers and readers. However, it is not that texts are autonomous, but that their alienation from humanity on three sides – the writer, the reader, the subject – as artifacts without responsibility, makes them appear so. That is, when responsibility for the content, and politics, of the text is waived, human surveillance turns upon itself and objectifies the author into an anonymous authoritarian tradition. Our conceptions of knowledge are reified in this manner.

It has become fashionable for anthropologists to congratulate themselves with remorseful exposures of the rhetorical turns of ethnographic language. It must be remembered that there is a rhetoric of rhetoric, and there is never a right way to write a monograph. What is positive about the ‘textual metaphor’ is that its very unresolved, and unresolvable, status generates adventurous attempts at writing new or different texts; it pushes further the concern with the relationship between theory and ethnography, and directs a rereading of previous texts in new or different ways. In this project no definite conclusion can, nor should, be reached. Each text, including this paper, could be opened again and again.

NOTES

1. This paper has suffered a great many readings and rewritings. Most thanks must go to Malcolm Crick and John Perry from Deakin University, without whom I could not have (re)written this at all. A number of others have read drafts and made comments. I would like to thank: Dipesh Chakrabarty, Greg Dening, Shirin Hanfi, Michael Healy, Jenny Lawrence, Don Miller, Michael Muetzelfeldt, Nikos Papastergiadis, Julie Stephens and Patrick Wolfe. None of these people, of course, can be blamed for what I have done.
2. Examples abound; perhaps a useful reference work – though I think it is an uneven representation of this newly created genre – is the volume *Writing Culture* (Clifford and Marcus (eds) 1986).
3. Although in anthropology, as Crick has pointed out, the work of Derrida, who only sometimes uses the term ‘deconstruction’, has not really been taken up (Crick 1985:73).
4. Deleuze and Guattari have said that there is no difference between what a book talks about and how it is made (Deleuze and Guattari 1983:3).
5. ‘Readingwork’ and ‘fieldwork’ do have their similarities.
6. A typology of which would (always) be premature, but Marcus and Cushman have made an important beginning (1982).
7. Such as Malinowski’s first chapter of *Argonauts of the Western Pacific*.
8. Geertz has quoted Nietzsche’s comment that even the self-hater prides himself on his moral sensitivity in discerning so acutely what a wretch he is (Geertz 1968:141 – Nietzsche not referenced).
9. Baudrillard has shown the contradictions of the anthropological endeavour as a dehumanising science: “For ethnology to live, its object must die. But the latter revenges itself by dying for having been ‘discovered’, and defies by its death the science that wants to take hold of it. Doesn’t every science live on this paradoxical slope to which it is doomed by the evanescence of its object in the very process of its apprehension . . . ethnology . . . [is] . . . a pure simulation” (Baudrillard 1983: 13-15). (Curiously enough, the ethnographic example Baudrillard uses here seems to have been a fiction cooked up by the cultural henchmen of the Marcos Philippines – the ‘revenge’ is all the more sweet since they were always a hoax.)
10. See Derrida’s commentary on the fragment of Nietzsche: ‘I have forgotten my umbrella’ (Derrida [1978] 1979).
11. “In science, each of us knows that what he has accomplished will be antiquated in ten, twenty, fifty years. That is the fate to which science is subjected; it is the very meaning of scientific work . . . Every scientific ‘fulfilment’ raises new ‘questions’; it asks to be ‘surpassed’ and outdated. Whoever wishes to serve science has to resign himself to this fact. Scientific works certainly can last as ‘gratifications’ because of their artistic quality, or they may remain important as a means of training. Yet they will be surpassed scientifically . . . We cannot work without hoping that others will advance further than we have. In principle, this progress goes on *ad infinitum* (Weber [1922] 1974). Weber’s description of science is compatible with the aims of this paper which examines selected anthropological monographs as ‘artistic’, ‘instructive’, soon to be outdated, ‘science’.

12. "The field and writing contexts are not distinct, of course . . . however, the difference between the researcher and the writer is still striking" (Crick 1982:17).
13. There are now too many ethnographies available to think that any one monograph will gain recognition unless it professes a new stylistic or theoretical approach. Rabinow's *Reflections*, justifiably, gains a substantial number of citations in the *Social Science Citation Index*.
14. The anthropologist's authority to present knowledge of the other is founded upon the status of the professional visitor, who is *not* a tourist (see Crick 1985).
15. There is a book on Morocco by Geertz, Geertz and Rosen, dated 1979, which may be the projected volume. Why is Rabinow not a contributor to this?
16. Wagner makes an interesting comparison between anthropologist and missionary: "An anthropologist is something of a 'culture missionary', believing (like all good missionaries) in the thing he invents, and is apt to acquire a substantial local following in his efforts to invent the local culture" (Wagner 1975:7n). It would be disturbing to suggest that Rabinow had invented Sidi-Lachen.
17. Again Marcus and Cushman have added to this point: "Rather than using the classic 'us/them', didactic form of device, experimental ethnographies have shifted to a self-reflexive 'me/them' form of contrast, which . . . invites readers to empathise with the revealed experience of the ethnographer, and in so doing to prepare themselves for discussions of cultural practices which while appearing radically different, will also seem authentic as well as plausible" (Marcus and Cushman 1982:50). A self-conscious 'recognition' has replaced observation as the keynote of method.
18. Rabinow is an editor in two books on Foucault (Dreyfus and Rabinow 1982; Foucault 1984). But Rabinow's reading in this discourse does not seem to have impressed him overly. He dismisses much of 'post-structuralism' quite quickly. Crick comments that the challenging writings of Foucault, Derrida, etc., may have a "flippant side" but that this entails "no holiday from serious study" (1985:86).
19. While in the field Dwyer anticipates the book he will write: "I had no definite idea what the public might be for such a text. I knew I would want it to be read by anthropologists . . ." (Dwyer 1982:177).
20. Richardson makes a suggestion which is relevant to the sort of project Dwyer planned in 1975. He sees an unwritten disciplinary obligation placed upon fieldworkers: "sooner or later the ethnographer feels that he must spend more time with his informant" (Richardson 1975:520).
21. Rabinow reproduces this as a put-down of Dwyer in unfavourable terms: "Dwyer's record of his exchanges with the Berber farmer demonstrate how thin and unreciprocal a relationship was established between them" (Rabinow 1985:7).
22. Rabinow claims that Dwyer's *Moroccan Dialogues* are written in "as white and flat a prose as can be imagined" (Rabinow 1985:3). However, the typographic alternations are clearly uneven.
23. Fernandez, or his editor/publisher, thought this photograph was so good it is included twice in the same text.
24. Male/female ethnographic teams have their own problems; see Gregory (1984).

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